

Implementation of Programme and Building SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) Villages with Lanterns of Knowledge

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Abstract

SDG's (Sustainable Development Goals) village is an area unit at the hamlet level that has certain criteria where there is an integrated and systematic Sustainable Development Goals program. SDG's village will later become a form or miniature model of the implementation of the SDGs program regionally and nationally. The purpose of holding the SDGs Village includes commitments global and national to improve the welfare of society includes 17 goals namely: (1) No Poverty; (2) No Hunger; (3) a Healthy and Prosperous Life; (4) Quality Education; (5) Gender Equality; (6) Clean Water and Proper Sanitation; (7) Clean and Affordable Energy; (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth; (9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure; (10) Reducing Gaps; (11) City and Sustainable Settlements; (12) Responsible Consumption and Production; (13) Climate Change Management; (14) Ocean Ecosystems; (15) Land Ecosystems; (16) Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions; and (17) Partnership for Achieving goals. This research is qualitative with purposive sampling. Data analysis techniques with qualitative descriptive, namely techniques that describe special things with data obtained through observation, interviews and documentation. From the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that Sukorejo Pondok Pesantren (PP) Rudlah Darussalam succeeded in building SDGs Villages and can be used as examples for other SDGs Villages. went smoothly. This is in the future to be sustainable in planning and implementing the agenda that has been planned so that it can be felt optimally.

Keywords: *SDG's (Sustainable Development Goals), village*

A. Introduction

The 20 SDGs Villages in Jember Regency include Sukorejo Pondok Pesantren (PP) Rudlah Darussalam aimed at anti-poverty villages, Sumber Waru-Sukowono namely food security village, Gebanglangkap-Panti a healthy and prosperous village, Cangkring-Jenggawah namely Smart Village, Gumuksari-Kalisat namely Good quality education, PP Ihyaus Sunnah Tugusari Bangsalsari namely clean water and sanitation villages, Pace-Silo, Karangrejo, Sumber Kejayan, Wringing Telu, Karanganyar, PP. At-Tanwir-Ledokombo, Kresek Pancakarya-Ajung, Tisno Gambar PP. Raudlatul Ulum Al-Ishaqi II Bangsalsari, Mojosari-Puger, Baban-Silo, Sumberweringin PP Raudlatu Syayab-Sukowono, Rambigundam PP. Maslahatul Ikhwan-Rambi Puji.

This SDGs Village has a focus on activities in various sectors including:

1. Social, namely:

- a) Education Scholarships
 - b) Entrepreneurship Training for Women
 - c) Inclusive village
 - d) Economics, namely:
 - e) food security (Sustainable Food House)
 - f) creative economy (making dish soap, training on making organic fertilizers, training on making wind oil, handicrafts, capital assistance for SDG's stalls)
 - g) Entrepreneurship (education to street vendors)
 - h) SDGs. stalls
2. Governance, namely:
- Cooperation with stakeholders (Fatayat NU, Muslimat, Ta'mir Masjid, Badan Amil Zakat National, Police, Government, PT Rajawali Nusindo, Universities, Habilis Indonesia Madani Foundation, NGOs etc). Environment namely:
- a) roadside flower planting, Sustainable Food House
 - b) Planting hybrid coconuts in community-owned gardens
 - c) Clean Water and Sanitation (Distribution of clean water from water sources to villages & construction of toilets)

The Programme of Stages:

- a) Survey database
- b) Database management
- c) FGD Temporary database results
- d) Database finalization

Assessment consists of:

- a) Data and Information about the problem.
- b) Data and information about basic needs
- c) Data and information on potential resources
- d) Data and information about existing stakeholders
- e) Data and information on troubleshooting
- f) Compilation of programs in the village that are detailed and systematic.

Implementation of the Program is as follows:

- a) Renovation of livable houses in 5 SDGs Villages, each with 3 houses
- b) Pace Village, Silo District Productive Economic Development: Livestock and Plantation (California Papaya Cultivation, and Cavendish Banana)

- c) Hybrid Coconut Cultivation
- d) Gumuksari Village, Sub-district of Kalisat for Productive Economic Development:
Paving Block

Cangkring Village, Jenggawah Productive Economic Development : Home Industry
Sumbercanting Village, Bangsalsari District. Productive Economic Development: Coffee
Processing Sukorejo Village, Bangsalsari District Productive Economic Development: Handy
Craft Development Mid-program evaluation is to evaluate when the program is in the
implementation process. Conduct a final evaluation of the program. This section describes the
monitoring and evaluation mechanism to see achievements implementation of the TPB/SDGs
Renaksi for each objective. The mechanism for monitoring and evaluating the TPB/SDGs
Action Plan needs to describe:

- a) Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanism

Contains a description of the methods and stages of monitoring and evaluating the
objectives, targets and indicators of TPB/SDGs and the feedback mechanism carried
out by each implementing team and the working group of each pillar.

- b) Reporting Mechanism

Contains the annual reporting systematics carried out by the central/regional
government with a description of the achievements of each goal, target, indicator,
efforts made, lessons learned, best practices, human stories, problems and challenges
faced for each TPB/SDGs objective, as well as policies, In addition, this report will also
contain descriptions of programs, activities, and budgets carried out by other
stakeholders, including Community Organizations and Media, Philanthropy and
Business Actors as well as Academics and Experts, and published so that they can be
accessed by the public.

- c) Execution time.

Contains the schedule for the implementation of monitoring and evaluation as well as
reporting on the achievement of the annual and five-year TPB/SDGs. This section
describes matters relating to the efforts and processes undertaken in the preparation of
the TPB/SDGs Renaksi, including the involvement of various parties by implementing
the following principles:

- 1) Universal: Implemented worldwide to transformative, people-centred,
comprehensive, and long-term goals and objectives,
- 2) Integration: Implemented in an integrated manner on all social,

- 3) economic and environmental dimensions (interrelated), and No-One Left Behind: Implemented by involving all stakeholders and providing benefits to all, especially the vulnerable. The principles of the TPB/SDGs partnership between stakeholders are as follows: trust building; equal partnership; Participation; Accountable; and mutually beneficial. This section also describes the principles for implementing the SDGs and efforts to strengthen the means of implementation.

Based on the description above, the formulation of the problem to be studied is "How is Implementation Program and Building SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) Villages with Lanterns of Knowledge?"

B. Results and Discussion

1) Theoretical Basis

Public policy according to Thomas Dye (1981:1) in Ristanto's book (2015) is whatever the government chooses to do or not to do. The scope of public policy is very broad, such as public policy in the fields of education, agriculture, health, transportation, defence and so on. In addition, viewed from the hierarchy, public policies can be national, regional, or local, such as laws, government regulations, provincial/district/municipal government regulations, and decisions of regents/mayors.

Policy implementation involves the efforts of policymakers to influence what Lipsky calls "street-level bureaucrats" to provide services or regulate the behaviour of the target group (target group). For simple policies, the implementation only involves one agency whose function is as an implementer. On the other hand, for macro issues, policies must involve various government institutions such as districts, sub-district, and village bureaucracies in dealing with poverty reduction in villages.

2) The following are theories on policy implementation

According to Theory C. Edward III in Subarsono's book (2015), policy implementation is influenced by four variables, including the following: Communication, namely the success of policy implementation requires the implementor to know what to do. What are the goals and objectives of the policy that must be transmitted to the target group so that it will reduce the distortion of implementation?

Resources are an important factor for effective policy implementation. The bureaucratic structure in charge of implementing policies has a significant influence on policy

implementation. One of the most important aspects of any organization is the existence of standard operating procedures (standard operating procedures or SOPs). Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that implementing a policy, is strongly influenced by the existence of clear communication both between individuals and between institutions, the fulfilment of the required resources, and the behaviour of good implementers.

The theory of Donald Van Meter and Carl Van Horn (1975) assumes that policy implementation runs linearly from public policy, implementor and performance of public policy performance. Some of these variables affect public policies such as communication between organizations in implementation activities, characteristics of implementing agents/implementors, and economic, social, and political conditions. Public policy in Donald Van Meter and Carl Van Horn's concept is divided into standards and objectives and resources related to communication between organizations in implementation activities, characteristics of implementing agents, economic, social, and political conditions, as well as the disposition of implementers who in turn ultimately affect the performance of the public policy.

The focus of research is very necessary so that researchers do not deviate from the goals that have been set. The definition of focus according to Moleong (2007:94) is that there are two goals that researchers want to achieve, namely: First, setting focus can limit the study. Second, the determination of focus serves to meet the inclusion-inclusion criteria or the entry-out criteria of information obtained in the field. Based on the conception of the research focus above, the focus of this Journal is the Implementation Program and Building SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) Villages with Lanterns of Knowledge.

This research approach is a descriptive qualitative approach. It means writing down what happened, where, how the process and the consequences. Provide a comprehensive picture of the existing reality. Sugiyono's opinion (2005:147) about the qualitative approach is to have the nature of the data or types of information collected to describe certain conditions, with separate words or sentences to obtain conclusions about the quality of distribution services.

The research approach uses Edward III Theory which includes 4 factors that influence the implementation of the BPNT Distribution Policy, namely Communication, Resources, Disposition and Bureaucratic Structure (as a reference). And the theory of Donald Van Meter and Carl Van Horn (1975) emphasizes the condition of society in the social, economic, and political fields. Location and Time The research was conducted in Sukorejo Village, Bangsalsari District, Jember Regency and started in January 2022.

As the author of this paper, I will analyze more deeply the SDGs Village Profile of Sukorejo Bangsal as follows: Food security village means Sustainable Food House which means In the SDGs Sukorejo village there is some vacant land with that students in the SDGs village assisted by the Jember baznas take advantage of and educate the community to move to use the empty land to plant vegetables and flowers with the aim of benefits and results. The harvest can be felt by the community or residents of the SDGs Sukorejo Bangsalsari Jember village.

(Pedoman Teknis Penyusunan Rencana Aksi Tujuan Pembangunan Berkelanjutan, 2020)

Anti-poverty village means the SDGs village stall, which means the SDGs village which is fostered by BAZNAS has a community economic empowerment program, one of which is providing business capital to MSME actors in SDGs Village. MSME actors who have received business capital assistance have been adjusted to the established criteria so that the provision of business capital assistance is expected to be right on target. The type of business assisted by BAZNAS is in the form of a food stall located right in front of the Secretariat of the SDGs Village Sukorejo – Bangsalsari. Developed and creative economy village means Fish Cultivation, which means Fish Pond Cultivation in SDGs Village has various types of freshwater fish, such as Tilapia, Gourami and Catfish. The results of fish farming are enjoyed by the local community. Another potential offered by SDGs Village is that the community and students who are doing internships, PPL or other research can immediately feel the excitement of fishing together in the pond. Fishing rods and bait have also been provided, making it easier for the community and students to fish.

An economically developed and creative village means the Telang Flower or *Clitoria ternatea* is known to increase vitality and a healthy ageing process. This flower is full of antioxidants, including proanthocyanidins (which support collagen and skin elasticity) and anthocyanins (which support healthy hair and eyes). In this SDGs Village, there are also several

telang flower plants. These flowers can be processed into telang flower tea which is very nutritious. The sour but refreshing taste of tea is considered to be efficacious in helping digestion and killing various bacteria.

Kampung Smart means Early Childhood Education Raudlah Darussalam which means Early Childhood Education Raudlah Darussalam was established in 2007 and is located on Jalan Balung, RT 01 RW 01, Sukorejo Village, Bangsalsari District, more precisely in the east and southeast of Darussalam Mosque. Raudlah Darussalam Early Childhood Education was organized by HM. Misbahus Salam, S.Ag. M. Pd.I and managed by Hj. Ilis Mahbubah, S.Ag. In this section of the Raudlah Darussalam Early Childhood Education page, various types of vegetables are planted which also serve as educational materials for preschool children to know more types of vegetables.

Madrasah Darussalam means Madrasah is a school or academy which is generally based on Islamic law. In this SDGs Village, there is Madrasah Darussalam which is a place for learning the knowledge of the Qur'an in the form of a TPA or Al-Qur'an Education Park. Kampung Inclusion means Darus Salam Center, namely DSC is an institution engaged in peace education to realize inclusiveness. DSC is a forum for SDGs village residents to be able to build effective communication with stakeholders across religions, races, cultures and groups. Clean Water and Sanitation Village mean Pipeline Assistance and MCK, namely Pipanization and MCK Making Assistance, which is intended to support the Environmental pillar in the SDGs. Provide facilities to the community to gain access to clean water and avoid pollution.

Village of Synergy and Sustainable Partnership means Functioning the Mosque, namely:

1. Baitullah, Place of Worship
2. Baitul Qur'an and Science
3. Baitul Mal
4. Baitul Mu'amalah

Clean Water and Sanitation Village mean Pipeline Assistance and MCK, namely Pipanization and MCK Making Assistance, which is intended to support the Environmental pillar in the SDGs. Provide facilities to the community to gain access to clean water and avoid pollution.

Village of Synergy and Sustainable Partnerships means Social Capital, namely Buying land for graves with cooperation and then waqf it Products SDGs Village Sukorejo Village Bangsalsari District Jember Regency. Mother's Washing Soap means Mother's washing soap

is a local product made by the residents of SDGs Village. Dish soap in general is sold at affordable prices but the quality is not inferior to other well-known or other products.

Madu Jahe means Kampung SDGs not only produces several products but also becomes a distributor and partner for other products such as this ginger honey, which is produced by UD. Mitra Mushroom, Jember. As for some relief of cough and throat symptoms, maintain body immunity and relieve muscle pain. So this ginger honey is very beneficial for the health of the human body. Snack Rds means the next product is crispy mushrooms, where this product is the original production of the residents of the SDGs Sukorejo Bangsalsari village. This crispy mushroom has many benefits, including strengthening the immune system, inhibiting the growth of cancer cells, lowering cholesterol and being healthy for the heart. In addition, this product also has a high selling value and is suitable for all ages

Petis Mercon Ummi means the next product that is no less interesting made by residents of the SDGs village, namely Petis Mercon "Umami" which is very suitable to be used as a food companion when relaxing. This "Umami" Mercon Petis can be a spice for rujakan, fried accompaniment and others.

Abon Ikan Tongkol means Shredded tuna is a product made from tuna as the main ingredient, where the SDGs village cooperates with the residents of Puget Jember village, which is the main fish-producing village in Jember. The benefits of tuna are, maintaining stable blood pressure, maintaining the function and health of body organs, and maintaining bone strength and body weight.

(Picture: Fish-Producing)

Beauty distributor in BCW products is an anti-ageing product for women's healthy and naturally beautiful skin. SDGs Village Women's Creativity is Being Bridal Makeup and other events. Bintang Songo rice distributor.

(the Picture : Rice of Production)

C. Conclusion

Implementation Program and Building SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) Villages with Lanterns of Knowledge are seen from the PBB cooperation from High to level Villages that have been coordinated. From the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that Sukorejo Pondok Pesantren (PP) Rudlah Darussalam succeeded in building SDGs Villages and can be used as examples for other SDGs Villages. Implementation Program and Building SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) Villages with Lanterns of Knowledge. went smoothly. This is in the future to be sustainable in planning and implementing the agenda that has been planned so that it can be felt optimally.

D. References

- Abu Huraerah, Pengorganisasian Dan Pengembangan Masyarakat; Model Dan Strategi Pembangunan Berbasis Kerakyatan, Humaniora, Bandung, 2008, Hlm.11. Pedoman Teknis Penyusunan Rencana Aksi Tujuan Pembangunan Berkelanjutan (TPB)/Sustainable Development Goals (Sdgs). 2020. Kementerian PPN/Bappenas. Edisi II. Jakarta.
- Adisasmita, Raharjo. 2011. Pembiayaan Pembangunan Daerah. Yogyakarta : Graha Ilmu
- Agustino, Leo. 2014. Dasar-Dasar Kebijakan Publik. Bandung: PT. Alfabeta
- Ali, Faried, Dkk. 2012. Studi Analisa Kebijakan (Konsep, Teori, Dan Aplikasi Sampel Teknik Analisa Kebijakan Pemerintah). Bandung: PT. Refika Aditama

- Badudu, J.S Dan Sultan Mohammad Zain, 2001. Kamus Umum Bahasa Indonesia, Jakarta : PT. Rineka Cipta
- Bahagijo, Sugeng Dkk. 2015. Panduan Sdgs Untuk Pemerintah Daerah (Kota Dan Kabupaten) Dan Pemangku Kepentingan Daerah. Jakarta : International NGO Forum On Indonesian Development (INFID)
- Dunn, W.N. 2003. Pengantar Analisis Kebijakan Publik. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press
- Effendi, Onong Uchjana, 2003. "Ilmu Komunikasi Dan Praktek Cetkan Kesembilan Belas. Bandung : PT Remaja Rosdakarya
- Jones, Charles O. 1985. Pengantar Kebijakan Publik (Public Policy). Jakarta: Rajawali Press
- Khomsan, Ali, Dkk. 2015. Indikator Kemiskinan Dan Misklasifikasi Orang Miskin. Jakarta : Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia.
- Mansur Fakih, Runtuhnya Teori Pembangunan Dan Globalisasi, Pustaka Pelajar, Yogyakarta, 1996.
- Nugroho, Riant. 2015. Kebijakan Publik Di Negara-Negara Berkembang. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Belajar
- Sastropetro, Santoso. 1982. Pelaksanaan Latihan. Jakarta : Gramedia
- Siagian, Sondang P. 1985. Filsafat Administrasi. Jakarta : Gunung Agung.
- Soekanto, Soerjono. 2010. Sosiologi Suatu Pengantar, Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Sdgs, Pusat Pengembangan Kampung. 2018. <http://jpicsvdruteng.com/tujuan-pembangunan-berkelanjutan-sdgs/pada-hari-senin-3-oktober-2022-pada-pukul-19.45-WIB>.